

NOTES

A New Approach to the Synthesis of the Trinuclear Complex, $H_2Fe_3(CO)_9PR$ (R=Alkyl or Aryl)

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Manuscript received 13 February 1991, accepted 27 May 1991

THE compound that is formed by refluxing $Fe_3(CO)_{12}$ with $PPhH_2$ in toluene medium is reported to be $H_2Fe_3(CO)_9(PR)$ ¹. But the same method where the reaction temperature is well above 100°, is quite understandably not suitable and is unsafe for reactions with low molecular weight gaseous phosphines like PCH_3H_2 . Attempts have therefore been made to develop an alternative method by applying milder reaction conditions thus reducing appreciably the vigour of the reaction with gaseous phosphines such that the formation of the expected compound may become a reality.

Experimental

All handlings of chemicals and the products were performed under nitrogen atmosphere. Organic solvents were dried and distilled. $Fe_2(CO)_9$ ² and the phosphines³ were prepared by the literature methods. Silica gel-60 was used for column chromatography.

Infrared spectra (cyclohexane) was measured on a Perkin-Elmer 297 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra ($CDCl_3$) on a Varian T60A (60 MHz) spectrometer. Mass spectra and C, H analyses were done in the laboratory of Prof. Dr. H. Vahrenkamp, University of Freiburg, Germany. CO contents were estimated by spectrophotometric method.

The synthetic methods for $Fe(CO)_4PCH_3H_2$ ^{4,5} and $Fe(CO)_4Pp-TolH_2$ ⁶ were modified to get better yields and purity.

Preparation of $Fe(CO)_4PCH_3H_2$ (1): $Fe_2(CO)_9$ (1.82 g, 5 mmol) suspended in benzene (50 ml), was kept under minimum exposure to external light. The freshly prepared and purified PCH_3H_2 gas was then slowly introduced into the suspension under constant stirring. Fresh aliquots of the phosphine gas was occasionally introduced into the reaction chamber in 10 min intervals and the process was continued for 2 h. The reaction mixture was then stirred further for 10 h for completion of the reaction. Benzene was then recovered by slow vacuum evaporation, and the liquid was subjected to fractional distillation under reduced pressure to

yield the product as an orange liquid (1.179 g, 64.3%).

Preparation of $Fe(CO)_4Pp-TolH_2$: A mixture of $Fe_2(CO)_9$ (1.82 g, 5 mmol), $Pp-TolH_2$ (Tol= $C_6H_4CH_3$) (0.62 g, 5 mmol) and benzene (40 ml) was stirred for 10 h. Benzene was then removed by slow vacuum evaporation and the resulting oily mass was extracted with n-hexane. Complete removal of hexane from the extract under reduced pressure yielded the product as orange-red liquid (1.38 g, 75.8%).

Preparation of $H_2Fe_3(CO)_9(PCH_3)$ (3): A mixture of $Fe(CO)_4PCH_3H_2$ (4.00 g, 18.5 mmol) and toluene (40 ml) was refluxed for 10 h. After cooling the volume of the reaction mixture was reduced to approximately 5 ml and then subjected to silica gel column chromatography. Fraction-1 was obtained by eluting with n-hexane. All solvents were removed under reduced pressure and the resulting solid was crystallised from n-hexane as orange-yellow crystals (1.07 g, 27%) of $Fe_2(CO)_6(PCH_3H)_2$ (4)^{5,6} as a mixture of isomers. Fraction-2 was obtained by eluting with n-hexane-toluene (10 : 1). All solvents were removed under reduced pressure and the resulting solid was crystallised from n-hexane-toluene (15 : 1) as red crystalline product (2.90 g, 72%).

Preparation of $H_2Fe_3(CO)_9(P-pTol)$ (5): $Fe(CO)_4Pp-TolH_2$ (5.00 g, 17.1 mmol) was taken in toluene (40 ml). Similar reaction conditions as above were applied and the reaction mixture was processed similarly to yield the product. Fraction-1 was obtained by eluting with n-hexane. All solvents were then removed and the resulting solid was crystallised from n-hexane as red crystals (3.18 g, 64%). Fraction-2 was obtained by eluting with n-hexane. All solvents were then removed and the resulting solid was crystallised from n-hexane to yield $Fe_2(CO)_6(P-pTolH)_2$ as orange crystalline mixture of isomers (1.04 g, 21%).

Results and Discussion

For better yields of $Fe(CO)_4PRH_2$ (1 and 2), longer reaction time and purification by fractional distillation or by solvent extraction were employed. Purification by silica gel chromatography did not function as the products got absorbed in silica gel and only a little amount came out when the polarity of the eluant was increased appreciably.

When 1 and 2 were brought into reaction in refluxing toluene, both bi- and tri-nuclear compounds $Fe_2(CO)_6(PRH)_2$ (4 and 6) and $H_2Fe_3(CO)_9(PR)$ (3 and 5) were formed (Table 1). Yield of the

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3 AND 5*

Compd. no.	Colour	M.p. °C	Mol. formula (Mol. weight)	m/z (mol. wt.)
3	Dark red	158	C ₁₀ H ₈ Fe ₃ O ₉ P (467.7)	468
5	Dark red	102	C ₁₆ H ₈ Fe ₃ O ₉ P (543.6)	544

*Compounds gave satisfactory C, H and Fe analyses.

compounds was dependent on the reaction time. A reaction time of 5–6 h was found to give maximum yields of 4 and 6 whereas 10–12 h for 3 and 5. The formation of the mono- and bi-nuclear compounds could clearly be ascertained from their typical ir bands in the ν_{CO} region⁴. The ir spectra (ν_{CO} region) of the compounds 3 and 5 indicated the presence of a triangular framework¹ (Table 2). The ¹H nmr

TABLE 2—IR AND ¹H NMR SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3 AND 4

Compd. no.	ν_{CO} cm ⁻¹	$\delta(R)^*$	J(Hz)	$\delta(H)$	J(Hz)
3	2 100m, 2 060s, 2 038vs, 2 010s, 1 988s, 1 972w	2.23d	9.6–	–23.68d	28.7
4	2 096m, 2 060m, 2 035vs	7.8m 2.49		–23.85d	30.0

*Substituent on phosphorus.

spectra showed the presence of hydrogen atoms between the two pairs of metal centres together with the CH₃ and *p*-Tol groups in 3 and 5 and the compounds consist of a triangular iron framework with a bridging μ_3 -PR unit situated at the top and two of the Fe–Fe bonds carrying bridging μ_2 -H atoms.

3; R=CH₃
4; R=*p*-Tol

The compositions of 3 and 4 were furthermore confirmed by the elemental analyses and molecular weight determinations by the mass spectral method.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Prof. H. Vahrenkamp for facilities and the authority of Jadavpur University, for granting a research fund.

References

- G. HUTTNER, J. SCHNEIDER, G. MOHR and J. VON SEYERL, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1980, **191**, 161.
- R. B. KING in "Organometallic Synthesis", eds. J. J. EISCH and R. B. KING, Academic, New York, 1965, Band 1.
- F. PASS, E. STEININGER and H. ZORN, *Monatsh Chem.*, 1962, **93**, 230.
- P. M. TRICHEL, W. K. DEAN and W. M. DOUGLAS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1972, **11**, 1609.
- R. L. DE and H. VAHRENKAMP, *Z. Naturforsch. Teil B*, 1986, **41**, 273.
- H. VAHRENKAMP, E. J. WUCHERER and D. WOLTERS, *Chem. Ber.*, 1983, **116**, 1219.